

Uncatalysed and catalysed oxidation of dextrose by *N*-bromosuccinimide in basic medium : A kinetic and mechanistic study

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Abstract : Kinetic investigation on uncatalysed and iridium trichloride catalysed oxidation of dextrose by alkaline solution of *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) have been carried out in the temperature range 25-45 °C. The reaction has been found to be first order with respect to each of oxidant and substrate in both uncatalysed and catalysed reaction. The reaction follows a first order dependence on OH⁻ ion concentration. A first order dependence on [catalyst] is also observed. Negligible effect of chloride ion on its higher concentration has been observed. Addition of succinimide shows a negative effect. The increase in ionic strength of the medium increases the rate of reaction. A 1 : 1 stoichiometry is observed in the oxidation. Effect of temperature on the rate of oxidation has been studied to show the validity of Arrhenius equation and various activation parameters have been computed.

Keywords : Kinetics, dextrose, *N*-bromosuccinimide.

Introduction

Aliphatic and aromatic *N*-halo¹ or *N*-halosulphonamide compounds are mild oxidizing agents, have been extensively used for the oxidation of a variety of organic compound including aldehydes, amines and amino acids. These oxidants contain strongly polarized *N*-linked halogens which are in the +1 oxidation state. It was reported earlier that the oxidation of sugars² with *N*-chlorobenzenesulphonamide and *N*-bromotoluenesulphonamide in alkaline solutions involves a sugar-to-oxidant stoichiometry of 1 : 1 for aldoses and 1 : 2 for fructose, and the products were identified as the corresponding aldonic acid for aldose and arabinonic acid for fructose. Most of the investigations of NBS acts only through its positive polar end producing Br⁺ which is subsequently solvated, thus H₂O⁺Br has been considered as the effective oxidizing species of NBS in acidic medium. In presence of mercuric acetate protonated form of NBS i.e. N⁺BSh has also been considered as reactive species of NBS in acidic medium³. *N*-Halosuccinimides are sources of positive halogens and these reagents have been exploited as oxidants for a variety of substrates in solution and mechanistic details are also available in few cases⁴. However, there are only few reports on the oxidation reactions of NBS in alkaline medium. Therefore these reactions have been studied in detail and the results are presented. *N*-Bromosuccinimide has been extensively used as an oxi-

dant in the study of kinetics and mechanism oxidation of both organic and inorganic substrates in acid medium. However, there is no report on the oxidation of any substrate by NBS in basic medium⁵. We present here the results of our investigations on the oxidation of dextrose by NBS in basic medium. An attempt has been made to identify the most probable reactive species of the oxidant in basic medium.

Results and discussion

The plots of log (*a* - *x*) versus time for variation of NBS concentration were linear, indicating a first order dependence of rate on [NBS]. The variations are given in Table 1. An increase in [substrate] leads to an increase in first order rate constant *k*. The plot of *k* versus [substrate] deviated from linearity at higher [substrate]. The plot of log (1/*k*) versus log (1/[dextrose]) was also linear, suggesting that the order of reaction decreases from unity to zero at higher [substrate]. The effect of alkali was studied at constant ionic strength maintained by NaClO₄. An increase in [OH⁻] leads to an increase in the first order rate constant *k*. The plot of *k* versus [OH⁻] deviated from linearity at higher [OH⁻]. However the plot of 1/*k* versus 1/[OH⁻] was linear. The plot of log 1/*k* versus log 1/[OH⁻] was also linear, suggesting that the order of reaction with respect to alkali or OH⁻ decreases from unity to zero at higher [OH⁻]. The rate increases with increase in [Ir^{III}] and the

Table 1. Effect of variation of [NBS], [dextrose], [OH⁻] and [IrCl₃] on reaction rate

[A] 10³ [NBS] = 4.00 mol dm⁻³; 10² [Dextrose] = 4.00 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [NaOH] = 1.00 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [NaClO₄] = 0.50 mol dm⁻³; Temp. = 303 K

[B] 10³ [NBS] = 2.00 mol dm⁻³; 10² [Dextrose] = 1.00 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [NaOH] = 1.00 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [NaClO₄] = 0.50 mol dm⁻³; 10⁵ [IrCl₃] = 1.54 mol dm⁻³; Temp. = 308 K

Uncatalysed [A]		Catalysed [B]	
10 ³ [NBS] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> (s ⁻¹)	10 ³ [NBS] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> (s ⁻¹)
1.00	0.34	1.00	2.22
2.00	0.41	1.50	1.59
3.00	0.36	2.00	1.47
4.00	0.40	3.00	1.59
5.00	0.40	4.00	1.59
6.00	0.48		
10 ² [Dextrose] (mol dm ⁻³)		10 ² [Dextrose] (mol dm ⁻³)	
2.00	0.16	0.50	0.50
3.00	0.24	1.00	0.97
4.00	0.34	1.50	1.27
5.00	0.40	3.00	2.17
6.00	0.50	4.00	2.84
8.00	0.66	6.0	3.21
10 ³ [NaOH] (mol dm ⁻³)		10 ³ [NaOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	
1.00	0.34	0.50	0.89
3.00	0.62	1.00	1.85
4.00	0.67	1.50	2.55
5.00	0.72	2.00	3.20
6.00	0.80	3.00	4.42
		4.00	5.66
		6.00	7.25
		10 ⁵ [IrCl ₃] (mol dm ⁻³)	
		1.20 ^a	2.50
		2.40 ^a	4.66
		3.60 ^a	6.32
		4.80 ^a	8.32
		6.00 ^a	10.6
		9.60 ^a	16.0

^a10² [Dextrose] = 4.00 mol dm⁻³.

results are summarized in Table 1. The plot of log *k* versus log [catalyst] was linear.

In alkaline medium and in absence of mercuric acetate, OBr⁻ has been considered as reactive species of

NBS according to following equilibria

Addition of the product (succinimide), decreased the rate of reaction. The effect of ionic strength was studied by carrying out investigations in the presence of different amounts of sodium perchlorate, which had a positive effect on the reaction rate. The effect of [Cl⁻] was studied by successive addition of potassium chloride in the reaction mixture. Addition of Cl⁻ ion showed a slight increase in the observed rate constant at lower [Cl⁻]. However, at higher [Cl⁻] the effect of Cl⁻ ion on the *k* was negligible and the results are summarized in Table 2. The rate of oxidation of sugars was studied at different temperatures in the range 298-318 K, and

Table 2. Effect of variation of [succinimide], [NaClO₄] and [Cl⁻] on reaction rate

[A] 10³ [NBS] = 5.00 mol dm⁻³; 10² [Dextrose] = 5.00 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [NaOH] = 1.00 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [NaClO₄] = 0.50 mol dm⁻³; Temp. = 303 K

[B] 10³ [NBS] = 2.00 mol dm⁻³; 10² [Dextrose] = 2.00 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [NaOH] = 1.00 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [NaClO₄] = 0.50 mol dm⁻³; 10⁵ [IrCl₃] = 1.54 mol dm⁻³; Temp. = 308 K

Uncatalysed [A]		Catalysed [B]	
10 ³ [Succinimide] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> (s ⁻¹)	10 ³ [Succinimide] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> (s ⁻¹)
1.00	0.33	0.50 ^a	4.98
2.00	0.23	1.00 ^a	4.60
4.00	0.16	2.00 ^a	4.32
6.00	0.13	3.00 ^a	3.83
8.00	0.10		
10.0	0.08		
10 ² [NaClO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)		10 ² [NaClO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	
2.00	0.50	1.00 ^b	1.22
4.00	0.58	4.00 ^b	1.60
8.00	0.66	8.00 ^b	2.11
12.0	0.75	12.0 ^b	2.57
16.0	0.83	16.0 ^b	3.14
		10 ³ [KCl] (mol dm ⁻³)	
		2.00	1.81
		4.00	1.78
		8.00	1.75
		12.0	1.77
		16.0	1.69
		20.0	1.71

^a10³ [NaOH] = 4.00 mol dm⁻³; ^b10² [Dextrose] = 1.00 mol dm⁻³.

the Arrhenius plot, $\log k$ versus $1/T$ was linear. The activation parameters were calculated for the composite reaction and shown in Table 3.

In alkaline solution, sugars undergo enolization to form enediolate anion, which has been shown in step (1). In the absence of other reactants, these anions undergo epimerization and isomerization^{6,7} to form a mixture of isomeric aldoses and ketoses. However in the presence of NBS, the endiolate anions (E^-) react with ^-OBr to form intermediate (X), which in turn undergoes cleavage to form the products. On the basis of experimental results and above discussions, the mechanism for the oxidation of dextrose by NBS in presence of Ir^{III} may be proposed as given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

According to above steps, the rate of disappearance of NBS may be given as

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = k_2 [E^-] [\text{NBS}] + k_7 [\text{Complex}] [\text{NBS}] \quad (8)$$

$$[E^-] = K_1[S][OH^-], [C_2] = K_3[C_1][H_2O]/[Cl^-],$$

$$[C_3] = K_4[C_1][OH^-]/[Cl^-],$$

$$[C_4] = K_5[C_3][OH^-]/[Cl^-]$$

$$= K_4K_5[C_1][OH^-]^2/[Cl^-]^2,$$

$$[\text{Complex}] = K_6[C_3][E^-]/[OH^-],$$

$$[\text{Complex}] = K_1K_4K_6[S][OH^-][C_1]/[Cl^-]$$

and

$[\text{Catalyst}]_T = [C_1] + [C_2] + [C_3] + [C_4] + [\text{Complex}]$
Thus the value of $[\text{Complex}]$ in terms of $[\text{Catalyst}]_T$ is obtained as

$$[\text{Complex}] = \frac{K_1K_4K_6[S][OH^-][Cl^-][\text{Catalyst}]_T}{K_3[H_2O][Cl^-] + K_4[OH^-] \{ [Cl^-] + K_5[OH^-] \} + K_1K_4K_6[S][OH^-][Cl^-]} \quad (9)$$

where, $K_3[H_2O] \gg [Cl^-]$ has been taken as suitable approximation in denominator.

On substituting the values of $[E^-]$ and $[\text{Complex}]$ in eq. (8), the rate law becomes,

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = K_1[S][OH^-][\text{NBS}] \left\{ k_2 + \frac{k_7K_4K_6[Cl^-][\text{Catalyst}]_T}{K_1[H_2O][Cl^-] + K_4[OH^-]} \right\} \{ [Cl^-] + K_5[OH^-] \} + K_1K_4K_6[S][OH^-][Cl^-] \quad (10)$$

Rate law (10) explains all the experimental results i.e. first order dependence of rate in $[\text{Oxidant}]$ in the absence as well as in the presence of catalyst. The decrease in order of reaction in substrate and alkali at higher $[\text{Substrate}]$ and $[OH^-]$ respectively in the presence of the catalyst is expected from the above rate law. Further, the rate law is in agreement with the plot of k versus $[\text{Catalyst}]$ which is linear with an intercept.

At higher $[Cl^-]$ where $[Cl^-] \gg K_5[OH^-]$ (as $IrCl_4(OH)_2^{3-}$ is unstable species), the rate law (10) becomes,

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = K_1[S][OH^-][\text{NBS}]$$

$$\left\{ k_2 + \frac{k_7K_4K_6[\text{Catalyst}]_T}{K_3[H_2O] + K_4[OH^-] + K_1K_4K_6[S][OH^-]} \right\} \quad (11)$$

which shows an independent nature of rate with respect to $[Cl^-]$ and in agreement with the experimental results. The observed positive salt effect is also in favour of the rate determining step (2) and (7) in which similarly charged species are involved.

Experimental

The reaction were carried out in a thermostatic regulated to within ± 0.1 °C. The solution of substrate and

Table 3. Effect of variation of temperature on reaction rate

Temp. (Kelvin)	Uncatalysed $10^4 k$ (s^{-1})	Catalysed $10^4 k$ (s^{-1})
298	0.25	-
303	0.40	1.65
308	0.70	2.13
313	1.08	3.40
318	-	4.03
Kinetic and thermodynamic parameters		
E_a^* (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	78.4	49.5
ΔG^* (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	75.8	46.9
ΔH^* (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	94.6	54.2
ΔS^* (JK $^{-1}$ mol $^{-1}$)	-61.9	-23.7

oxidant were kept in black coated separate bottles. These solutions were kept in the thermostat to attain the thermostatic temperature. The appropriate quantity of oxidant was added to substrate containing other reagents and the reaction bottle was shaken well. The course of the reaction was followed by immediately withdrawing 10 ml of the reaction mixture at a definite interval of time and added to a solution of KI in a flask to quench the reaction. The unreacted oxidant quickly react with the KI solution and liberates iodine which has been titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate solution using starch solution near the end point as indicator. Different studies such as variation of substrate (dextrose), oxidant (NBS), sodium hydroxide, succinimide, potassium chloride and the temperature were carried out. In the complete investigations oxidant concentration was always kept low as compared to the concentration of substrate. The reproducibility of results were found to be always within the permissible limit.

Stoichiometry : Stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by taking *N*-bromosuccinimide in large excess as compared to dextrose in different ratios. Reaction mixture containing sugar, NaOH, catalyst and *N*-bromosuccinimide (in excess) were equilibrated for 42 h at room temperature (~ 30 °C) excess of oxidant was determined iodometrically. The stoichiometric results may be represented by following equation.

Product analysis : Reduction product succinimide was detected by spot test analysis⁸. The aldonic acid were confirmed by the help of equivalence, kinetic studies, and paper chromatography. Thus the stoichiometry and product of oxidation of dextrose by NBS in acidic and alkaline media is same but their kinetic patterns are different. The negative value of entropy of activation is accounted for by the fact that as the intermediate complex decomposes in the rate determining step.

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